

Measuring Outcomes of Business Analytics: A Challenge

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ABSTRACT

Business analytics uses statistical techniques like regression, classification, data mining, NLP-text mining (Neuro-Linguistic Programming), etc. to elucidate patterns in data and come up with data-driven decisions to gain insight into the company's performance. The methodological challenges while measuring outcomes range from availability and access to quality data; incorporating moderating variables of interest in the business models and conducting longitudinal studies instead of cross-sectional studies to elicit better solutions in the organizational values.

Keywords: Business Analytics (BA); Outcomes; Decision making

INTRODUCTION

Business analytics is defined by Evans (2012) as the "use of data, information technology, statistical analysis, quantitative methods, mathematical or computer-based models to help managers gain insight about their business operations and make better fact-based decisions".

Business analytics uses statistical techniques like regression, classification, data mining, NLP-text mining (Neuro-Linguistic Programming), etc. to elucidate patterns in data and come up with data-driven decisions to gain insight into the company's performance. Raw data is cleaned and the four types of analysis important to make decisions are: *descriptive analysis*- which identifies a trend in data variables; *diagnostic analysis*- are used to elicit association using regression and classification algorithms; *predictive analysis*- which uses machine learning techniques to forecast future outcomes and *prescriptive analysis*-using AI (Artificial Intelligence- Neural networks) which uses retrospective data to prescribe solutions for the future.

Results of a study done by Price Water Cooper (PwC, 2016) of 2100 senior executives of an automotive company were *somewhat data-driven* (48%) and *highly data-driven* at forty-six percent. Most of them used diagnostic or predictive analysis for their decision making and 6% of *rarely data-driven* individuals used only descriptive analysis to formulate their judgments.

As large amounts of information are generated and the business analytic tools are very helpful in identifying changes in the market and take decisions accordingly, but the quality of the data, its resources, and the adaption of its results in a responsible manner is also important (Ramakrishnan et al., 2012). Therefore this review is going to look into the challenges of measuring outcomes from business analytic tools.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Team work

To make sense of data by measuring the outcomes needs a team of the following - *data scientists*- who obtain, prepare, and model the data; *business analysts* with domain knowledge and use data to create business value and solutions, and *IT professionals*-who improve and set up the data science elucidations. The team can also involve doctoral students by collaborating with research intuitions. Such effective teams can focus on the data to solve problems efficiently and even use data for further experimentation (Vidgen and Wang, 2009). Measuring outcomes from data is not just numbers to make sense of the data at hand; the data scientist may not be computer engineers but they must work as a team, be inquisitive and focus on the unique business problems, and work cross-functionally to create solutions and business values.

Skills Shortage

Many organizations have huge amounts of data but they are baffled with what and how to use it effectively to gain knowledge from the information at hand and how to advance the business (Evans, 2012 and LaValle et al., 2010). Moreover, lack of skilled analysts; slow uptake of evidence-based decision making; dearth of Return on Investment (ROI) variables to be included in the models; skeptics do not accept data-based strategy; want of methods to convert

structured and unstructured data into actionable analytics; the cost of training people in the organization about data analytics are all issues that need to be handled to have a value-based ethos (Sharda et al 2017).

Data analysis skills and training for the same can be provided by the organization so that using analytic tools for an enhanced decision can be built into the company's culture (Vidgen and Wang, 2009).

Organizational Culture

Business analytics can be successful in those organizations that are committed to improving their performance, productivity, and innovation facets (Norris et al., 2009). This effort will translate into wise decisions and judgments; it will enhance the policies and procedures to boost performance; it will improve the value and help to train and educate the workforce towards assessment oriented and analytic type of thought process and increase the transparency of performance in the organizational setup.

Data Quality

The most significant issues with Big Data are -the availability, quality, and access to appropriate data resources. Collection and analysis of data have to be an organizational effort and not just an IT departmental issue (Vidgen and Wang, 2009). The other issues with data quality is that should there be the usage of validated questionnaires or theoretical frameworks should dictate the research protocol, as such theoretical frameworks that are not validated can bias data collection and eventually interpretation of the data and can this issue be sorted with the inclusion of open-ended interviews to the research methodology?? (Bazeley, 2007).

Moderating Variables

The role of moderating variables is very important and is often a neglected aspect while measuring outcomes for business analytics. One of the challenges in measuring outcomes with business analytic is selecting the appropriate variables/ indicators of interest, for example, flexible IT infrastructure in market compositions (Bhatt et al., 2010); top management assurance and organizational attitude, etc.(Ramanathan et al., 2017).

A study by Ramanathan et al (2017) found that even although business analytic applications cannot directly improve a company's performance; process-level performance variables as mediators in this direction of association also have to be taken into consideration. In short business, analytics gives benefits to the business processes which in turn enhances the company's performance.

Research Methodology

Cross-sectional studies have lower-quality outcomes in terms of establishing causality as compared to longitudinal ones. Conduct of studies on inappropriate sample sizes; inability to extrapolate results of studies done in developing nations are some of the issues that affect outcomes. Some studies lack theoretical underpinnings or empirical proof to substantiate their hypothetical claims. There is a clear lack of understanding of one aspect of business analytics and that is how to measure outcomes on performance (Operational and Financial performance).

What to measure?

A study was done by Nichols (2008) on the impact on marketing for example for a consumer who wants to buy a Camry Toyota car, gets information simultaneously from TV ads, Google and YouTube from her phone, billboard advertisements, etc. this media mix modeling and the latest predictive analysis where the last click on the ad by the consumer can measure the cause-effect relationship between the ad and purchasing. Due to the exponential growth of cloud computing, cheap data storage, cloud-based analytics can measure the performance of the ads on different social media sites, the sales, competing offerings in one place in an instant, and this can enhance marketing and sales by 10-30 percent.

Newer analytic methods have three major attributes: *attribution* –it quantifies the influence of each element; *optimization*: predictive modeling that can run scenarios for business planning and *allocation*- distribution of resources.

Attribution- The issues projected by most companies is that there is inadequate data and they do not think of data from different departments likes sales, finance, distribution, customer service as one Big Data and do not know where and how to focus ... therefore to model their business plan, the study states that they should focus mandatorily on the following: competitive activities, market condition, marketing action, consumer response, and business outcomes.

Optimization- In the car example, the consumer was convinced of buying the car based on series of simultaneous equation statistical modeling technique that assembles various variables at a single snapshot view and explains the consumers marketing behaviour. These models help to measure 'elasticity' (ratio of percentage change of one variable affects the percentage change in the other variable) assigned to each variable known as a business driver. Knowledge of how the business drivers fluctuate one can predict the specific changes to the outcomes. Therefore the collection of vast

data on business drivers and optimization software tools help to predict sales and even what-if scenarios and changes in the exogenous variables.

Allocation- is putting up the results of the attribution and optimization into the market to validate models and measure outcomes and then allocate resources accordingly with better precision and accountability.

In Summary...

To overcome the challenges of measuring outcomes in business analytics the following rules may help...

- To overcome resistance towards the implementation of business analytics the senior management should be clear about its importance and align the organization towards its early steps.
- The management should appoint a multi-talented manager or director as a project head with a good analytic based attitude with good business planning, finance, and marketing skills.
- Treat the data from all the departments of the company as intellectual property with a defined asset value
- Start with smaller scale models to win the confidence of the company and generate an attitude of analysis as the culture of the organization
- Test the model belligerently with different scenarios and keep feeding it back into the original model

CONCLUSION

This review provides a summary of the issues of measuring outcomes and making sense of data with business analytics. We identified that analyzing data and coming up with optimal solutions is teamwork of data scientists, business analysts, and IT professionals. The review identified that analyzing data and coming up with optimal solutions is teamwork of data scientists, business analysts, and IT professionals. The methodological challenges while measuring outcomes range from availability and access to quality data; incorporating moderating variables of interest in the business models and conducting longitudinal studies instead of cross-sectional studies to elicit better solutions in the organizational values.

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